

CREAF OPEN SCIENCE POLICY

2025

SHAPING THE FUTURE OF SCIENCE: OPEN, COLLABORATIVE, AND INTEGRITY-DRIVEN

Through this policy, CREAM adopts and integrates the principles and ambitions of the Open Science model into its organizational culture, establishing specific responsibilities to support implementation and making Open Science a strategic priority.

CREAF OPEN SCIENCE POLICY

This Policy has been approved by the Director of CREAM and takes effect from 31 July 2025. It will be reviewed and updated at least every three years.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AI: Artificial Intelligence

APC: Article Processing Charges

CARE: Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics

CC: Creative Commons

CERIF: Common European Research Information Format

CRedit: Contributor Role Taxonomy

CRIS: Current Research Information System

CTA: Copyright Transfer Agreement

DMP: Data Management Plan

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

IP: Intellectual Property

OA: Open Access

ORCID: Open Researcher and Contributor ID

ORRI: Open and Responsible Research and Innovation

OS: Open Science

PID: Persistent Identifier

PRC: Publish-Review-Curate

ROR: Research Organization Registry

SDG: Sustainable Development Goal

INTRODUCTION

Open Science (OS) is a transformative paradigm in the scientific landscape, reshaping how scientific knowledge is funded, created, shared, used, and assessed. Evolving from a bottom-up movement in the 80s and 90s, OS seeks to dismantle the 'Ivory Tower' perception of academia as isolated from society. Its primary goal is to improve the quality, relevance, and societal value of research.

As a cornerstone of broader movements towards open knowledge and Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI), complementary to the principles of slow science and supported by metascience, the OS model contributes to:

- Accelerating scientific discovery and innovation to address urgent crises and broader societal goals, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), by democratizing access to high-quality, comprehensive knowledge.
- Enriching global intellectual heritage with diverse insights and innovative approaches derived from interdisciplinary collaborations and traditional knowledge.
- Improving sustainability and efficiency, reducing duplication of efforts and waste of resources, sharing results, infrastructure and research information, standardizing protocols, fostering re-usability and new applications, optimizing processes and promoting an agile work environment.
- Mitigating the reproducibility crisis by sharing raw data, the code used for data analysis, or pre-registering studies.
- Building research integrity to prevent or reduce bias, negligent or questionable research practices, and misconduct, increasing public trust in science, and reliability.
- Reversing the academic pressure to produce, encouraging curiosity-driven research projects and cultivating a 'publish for purpose' spirit, allowing for a more thorough, methodical, collaborative research.

The CREAM Open Science Policy articulates our vision and commitments to advancing and strengthening the OS model. We recognize openness both as an end to sharing knowledge and building trust and as a means to improving research quality. Through this policy, CREAM formally adopts and integrates OS principles and ambitions into its organizational culture, establishing specific responsibilities to support implementation and making OS a strategic priority.

The Policy builds on standard-setting international, European, national, and regional frameworks and enablers, including but not limited to: the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021), the EU's Open Science Policy (European Commission, 2019), the Spanish National Open Science Strategy (Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación, 2023), the

Catalan Open Science Strategy (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2024), the CERCA Open Data-Data Management Strategy (CERCA, 2020) and Code of Conduct (CERCA, 2018), the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (Kramer et al., 2024), CoARA's Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (Arentoft et al., 2022), the OS Taxonomy (Pontika et al., 2015), and the ORRI Taxonomy (Nieminen, 2024), among others. Additionally, this Policy supports the requirements from the European Commission's research and innovation funding programmes and relevant regulations, including the GDPR (Regulation 2016/679). Finally, it complements the terms set forth in other institutional documents, especially the CREAM Intellectual Property Policy (CREAF, 2025c).

PURPOSE, SCOPE AND TARGET AUDIENCE

The CREAM Open Science Policy establishes baseline standards and guiding principles to adapt and integrate the OS model into our organizational culture. This Policy contributes to ensuring consistent practices across the institution, aligning with funder requirements and best practices for research management and assessment, and covering the broad aspects of OS while remaining flexible to accommodate specific needs and future developments.

This Policy provides an overarching framework, and it intentionally does not delve into the practical elements of implementing and monitoring OS practices at CREAM. Specifically, this policy does not cover detailed procedures or specific infrastructure and resources. These granular aspects are instead outlined in our service catalogue, operational protocols, evaluation frameworks, and toolkits, all of which can be found in CREAM's intranet (CREAM, 2025b).

It is recommended that this Policy be read together with the CREAM Open Science Glossary (CREAM, 2025a), which includes detailed descriptions of the specific terms used in the context of this document.

ACTIVITIES COVERED

The mandates of this policy apply to all activities conducted at CREAM or with CREAM resources, including but not limited to:

- Funded projects
- Service commissions
- Collaborations
- PhD programmes

APPLICABLE OUTPUTS

This policy applies to outputs and contributions to knowledge produced, authored, co-authored or overseen by individuals engaged in activities at CREAM, including but not limited to:

- **Scholarly materials:** peer-reviewed publications, conference papers and presentations, preprints and working papers, books and book chapters, monographs, theses and dissertations.
- **Research data and documentation:** research datasets and associated metadata, data management plans (DMP), lab notebooks and methodologies, preregistration plans, project-specific OS plans, etc.
- **Computational outputs:** research software, applications, code, algorithms, programming scripts, and computational models.
- **Dissemination, outreach, and educational resources:** books and book chapters, brochures, infographics, posters, public engagement and audiovisual content, workshops and seminar materials, teaching materials, and learning objects derived from research activities.
- **Institutional outputs:** technical documents, annual reports, policy briefs, etc.

STAKEHOLDERS

This policy applies to internal staff, either permanent or temporary, executing or supporting research at our institution, hereafter referred to as “CREAF staff”:

- Individual researchers at all career levels
- Research teams
- Research managers and administrators

Accommodation for special cases is addressed in the following sub-section, “Limitations and exceptions.”

LIMITATIONS AND EXCEPTIONS

CREAF frequently engages in collaborative activities with various stakeholders. To ensure flexibility while maintaining our commitment to OS, this Policy acknowledges the need for adaptable practices in these special cases through specific agreements:

- **Affiliated researchers** hold positions at multiple institutions, contributing to CREAM's activities, projects, or research initiatives.
- **Visiting researchers** join CREAM for a specific period, such as a semester or academic year, usually to collaborate on research or teach.

- **Collaborators from partner institutions** work together on specific joint projects or initiatives while remaining employed at their respective institutions, including universities, research institutions, and sometimes industry and other private sector partners. This collaboration is often formalized through agreements between the institutions involved (e.g., research consortia).
- **Scholarships and fellowships** often provide funding for students or researchers to conduct research at CREAM to enhance their academic and professional development.
- **PhD candidates** may conduct significant portions of their research at CREAM.
- **Students**, particularly at the undergraduate and master's levels, often undertake final projects as part of their degree requirements, involving activities conducted at CREAM.
- **Citizen scientists and end users** contribute to scientific research without formal employment or affiliation to CREAM, but in collaboration with CREAM's professional scientists.

The Policy also addresses scenarios involving third-party agreements:

- When research activities are funded by a third party with OS mandates stricter than CREAM's –i.e., they require more rigorous compliance with OS principles–, the agreements with that party will take precedence over this policy.
- In cases where the third party imposes less stringent requirements without reasonable justification, CREAM reserves the right to maintain institutional OS standards as the baseline.

RIGHTS AND RESPONSIBILITIES

GENERAL PROVISIONS

1. CREAF is responsible for:

- a. Securing the resources necessary for providing, improving and maintaining suitable support, including accessible services and infrastructure, to enable CREAF staff to fulfil their OS responsibilities and ensure open as possible –ethical, legal and safe– scientific knowledge access and reuse.
- b. Fostering an environment that upholds research ethics and integrity, implements robust quality control mechanisms, and safeguards academic freedom.
- c. Embedding OS principles in institutional protocols and guidelines, including but not limited to outputs management, research assessment, and IPR. Policies must ensure that all aspects of OS are coherent and mutually reinforcing.
- d. Developing a flexible framework that accommodates diverse collaborative –national or international– scenarios. These may include harmonizing OS practices and data management protocols in partnership with collaborating institutions as needed, or using common metadata standards to ensure interoperability and ease of data sharing across organizations.
- e. Defining clear roles for OS implementation, including but not limited to appointing an Open Science manager.
- f. Providing CREAF staff with training on principles, practices and tools to enhance OS literacy and uptake and to navigate ethical, privacy, and data security issues. Training should be focused on the entire research lifecycle and provided for all career levels.
- g. Ensuring that access to institutional resources –either public-facing, internal or hybrid– meets diverse user needs while safeguarding critical data and information.
- h. Maintaining ownership and control of CREAF's IPR, including the authority to define reuse licences. This approach ensures our work is widely accessible, while preserving our ability to manage and protect our intellectual assets.
- i. Establishing and maintaining an ethical review process for all partnerships and funding arrangements by following internal protocols and codes of conduct to ensure they align with our institutional values and commitment to OS principles.

- j. Aligning OS compliance and monitoring mechanisms with relevant mandates and ensuring ongoing policy effectiveness.
- k. Promoting the participation in OS communities, supporting initiatives that advance and empower OS, and engaging with other institutions to share best practices.
- l. Encouraging researchers to voluntarily exceed funder requirements and ensure openness to the entire research lifecycle as early as possible while respecting any necessary restrictions, as much as reasonably possible.
- m. Advocating for transparent data analysis, swift error correction, purposeful publishing, and slow science principles—prioritizing thoughtful, rigorous research and long-term programs over rapid output.
- n. Encouraging researchers –especially seniors, leaders, and supervisors- to be role-models for their team members in practicing OS.
- o. Encouraging private sector collaborators to implement OS principles and practices in their activities.

2. **CREAF staff is responsible for:**

- p. Complying with the organizational, regulatory, institutional, and other contractual and legal requirements related to the funding, production, curation, deposit, management, distribution and use of outputs in case there is no other agreement with third parties taking precedence.
- q. Upholding and promoting the highest standards of research integrity and ethical conduct in their work, encompassing both scientific activities and research support functions.
- r. Participating in OS training programmes, as well as ethical, privacy, and data security issues, when applicable.
- s. Integrating OS principles into both scientific and research management activities throughout the research lifecycle, when applicable.
- t. Keeping up-to-date records of their OS contributions to report their scientific, research management & other activities when needed.
- u. Ensuring their public outputs are accessible, reproducible and reusable, and preventing knowledge fragmentation, making them as open as possible and as closed as necessary.
- v. Choosing the appropriate type of licensing for their outputs, preferably allowing free distribution and reuse with proper attribution.

- w. Prioritizing the use, sharing, and contribution to OS commons –such as open bibliographic databases, open software, open educational resources, or publishers offering open rights retention agreements– whenever practicable, considering third-party requirements, security considerations, and resource availability.
- x. Providing references when reusing data, materials, software, and tools.

RESEARCH ETHICS AND INTEGRITY

Researchers are responsible for:

- y. Conducting research ethically and responsibly, being accountable for the integrity of the research process, their published work and for the social, environmental, and human health impacts of their findings. They must adhere to the highest standards of research ethics and integrity as outlined in professional guidelines, such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA, 2023).
- z. Disclosing all actual or potential conflicts of interest and funding sources that could influence their work or its interpretation, such as through formal statements in published papers.
- aa. Reporting all necessary information about potential partnerships or funding opportunities to ensure they align with CREAM's values and commitment to OS principles.
- bb. Upholding integrity when communicating research findings to diverse audiences, including the media and policymakers: provide accurate and validated content in clear and accessible language, avoid sensationalism, stress the limitations and implications of their work, and safeguard sensitive or confidential information.
- cc. Conducting peer reviews responsibly and with respect, ensuring that their assessments are timely, fair, unbiased, and based solely on the scientific merit of the work under review. Reviews should be thorough, constructive, and aimed at improving the quality of research. Criticisms should be specific and substantiated with evidence. Researchers are encouraged to participate in open peer-review processes.
- dd. Reporting any suspected research misconduct, plagiarism, or ethical concerns to the appropriate authorities.
- ee. Considering the ethical implications of OS practices, particularly regarding data privacy, informed consent, and potential misuse of research findings by third parties.

- ff. Managing data accessibility when full openness is limited by ethical, privacy, confidentiality, security concerns, or third-party restrictions. In such cases, they should: (1) Clearly outline the limitations in the data availability statement, (2) Implement protective measures, such as data sharing agreements, anonymizing personal data or employing controlled access and encryption methods, and (3) consider alternative sharing options like synthetic datasets or data aggregation.
- gg. Respecting indigenous data sovereignty when research affects indigenous communities, ensuring collective benefit, acknowledging their authority to control data and traditional ecological knowledge, and fulfilling responsibilities to engage respectfully.
- hh. Identifying and minimizing potential risks to ecosystems, including protected habitats and populations of endangered or otherwise fragile species, especially when conducting field studies or collecting observations in the wild. Researchers are encouraged to reuse protocols and data to minimize or avoid significant harm to ecosystems, habitats, and individual organisms. Moreover, researchers are encouraged to minimize their carbon and water footprint during their activities, whenever possible, including but not limited to academic travel (fieldwork, meetings, conferences), use of energy-intensive equipment and AI data centres.

IDENTIFIERS, AFFILIATIONS, ATTRIBUTION, AND RIGHTS RETENTION

CREAF staff is responsible for:

- ii. Consistently and accurately acknowledging their affiliation with CREAF in all research outputs that include contributions from CREAF, either using the official institutional name, the ROR ID or the CREAF logo, when appropriate.
- jj. Creating and maintaining a single digital identity with ORCID, when appropriate, and using it consistently across research activities and outputs for author disambiguation.
- kk. Ensuring their research outputs are assigned with PIDs such as DOIs, avoiding duplicating identifiers for each individual output to prevent fragmented citation counts and metadata inconsistency.
- ll. Assigning appropriate authorship, based on these principles: (1) all authors should have made substantial contributions to the work –conception, design, data acquisition, analysis, interpretation, drafting, or critical revision–, (2) all authors should be able to take public responsibility for the content and be accountable for all aspects of the work, and (3) author order should reflect the level of contribution.

- mm. Ensuring fair attribution and recognition of contributors and facilitators that do not meet full authorship criteria, including but not limited to thesis supervisors, data collectors, software developers, graphic designers, citizen scientists, funders, and donors: use standardized attribution systems like CRediT, acknowledge them individually or as a group in the acknowledgments section, or recognize them through data citations of datasets in the reference list.
- nn. Ensuring rights retention by applying a CC BY licence or equivalent to their outputs at submission. Transferring exclusive rights to the publisher is not permitted. They must read journal policies and CTAs to check for terms that may conflict with the OA conditions of their grant agreements or employment and request amendments or an author addendum.
- oo. Citing or referencing all outputs used in research, either those produced by CREAM or externally sourced. This practice facilitates access, provides appropriate credit and attribution, supports the claims made in the research, and enables verification.

DISSEMINATION, PRESERVATION, REPRODUCIBILITY, AND REPLICABILITY

Researchers are responsible for:

- pp. Ensuring compliance with OS and data management requirements set by funders, PhD programs, etc. as well as adhering to relevant disciplinary standards and guidelines.
- qq. Ensuring research integrity if they choose to publish their work, selecting quality and legitimate scientific outlets, such as journals, platforms or books. Researchers are encouraged to bibliodiversify their publishing practices to enrich the global scholarly conversation by submitting work in a variety of languages, formats and venues, conducting research in underrepresented or emerging fields, etc.
- rr. Ensuring immediate OA to peer-reviewed publications, either by publishing in an OA journal or by depositing the published version or the postprint in a trusted digital repository without embargo and for at least 10 years, or by combining both pathways. Whenever possible, the Diamond model or the Green route take precedence over APC-based models, whereas the Hybrid and Bronze models are not encouraged due to ethical reasons and the potential risk of losing the scholarly record.
- ss. Documenting the research process—including data management planning, hypotheses, methods, analyses, and findings—comprehensively and accurately, regardless of the results. They are also encouraged to fully disclosing their procedures and, when appropriate, pre-registering study hypotheses and analysis plans.

- tt. Creating, updating and adhering a DMP in accordance with the FAIR principles —and, where applicable, the CARE principles— for every research activity they coordinate that involves the use of data. This requirement applies regardless of whether the data is collected by the researchers themselves or obtained from external sources. Researchers are encouraged to publicly share their DMPs in an appropriate repository, provided that doing so does not compromise ethical, legal, or sensitive data considerations.
- uu. Ensuring the integrity of data underlying the results with data protection measures to safeguard against unauthorized access, tampering or misuse, rigorous quality control measures, and encouraging attempts at replication.
- vv. Depositing the data, code, protocols, clear and detailed documentation and other materials necessary to reproduce and replicate their findings in a structured format — such as a replication package— into a trusted digital repository. Depositing raw data takes precedence over processed data whenever feasible. Researchers must comply with relevant ethical, legal, and data security requirements, particularly concerning sensitive or personal data, and justify limitations on making data open, when applicable, to ensure compliance with regulations, foster trust, mitigate concerns about misconduct, and facilitate the reproducibility of results.
- ww. Ensuring that metadata is openly accessible under a standard open licence in all cases. This metadata guarantees that data, regardless of its accessibility status, remains findable.
- xx. Adding an availability statement to manuscripts, outlining where both research outputs and inputs can be accessed.
- yy. Prioritizing the use of and contributing to open-source tools, codes, hardware, and software, whenever possible. This enables replication, further development of findings, and the identification of methodological errors or limitations.

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APPENDIX A: OPEN SCIENCE FOUNDATIONS AND CHALLENGES

THE PILLARS OF OPEN SCIENCE

The OS model is founded on a comprehensive framework of principles and dimensions, designed to foster and support an ‘open science mindset’ that permeates every stage of the research lifecycle.

CORE PRINCIPLES

- **Transparency:** Making research processes, tools, and outputs openly available.
- **Accessibility:** Ensuring that everybody has universal access to scientific knowledge and research outputs, particularly those funded by public resources, by removing barriers to information, data, and research findings.
- **Collaboration and reciprocity:** Encouraging the mutual exchange of knowledge, resources, and support among researchers and institutions across disciplines, sectors, and geographical scopes. Reciprocity emphasizes that collaboration should be a two-way street, where contributions are recognized and reciprocated.
- **Replicability and reproducibility:** Enabling others to replicate, validate results and build upon scientific work.
- **Ethics and integrity:** Protecting research subjects, considering the consequences of their work, and following research conduct standards.
- **Inclusivity:** Embracing diversity in perspectives, experiences, participants, and beneficiaries of research to enrich the scientific discourse and outcomes.

SUPPORTING PRINCIPLES

Essential for fostering a responsible OS environment are data security aspects:

- **Protecting privacy and sensitive data:** Implementing personal data managing protocols and establishing secure platforms for controlled access to sensitive datasets.
- **Safeguarding intellectual property:** Sharing of research outputs while respecting authorship, rights retention, licensing and patenting processes, thereby encouraging innovation and collaboration within a secure framework.

- **Preventing misuse:** Implementing robust protective measures, such as controlled access protocols, safeguards research data and knowledge from potential misuse. These precautions are essential in preventing abuse and contribute significantly to the protection of vulnerable entities, including endangered species and fragile ecosystems.

DIMENSIONS

The ambitions of the OS movement can be summarized in these seven pillars:

1. **OA to publications:** Ensuring research literature is freely available online and as early as is practical in the discovery process.
2. **FAIR research data management:** Implementing the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles for scientific data.
3. **OS support structure:** Facilitating the uptake of OS practices through dedicated platforms, guidelines and services.
4. **Training and skills development:** Educating researchers on OS practices and tools.
5. **Incentives and assessment:** Reforming research evaluation systems and metrics to recognize and reward OS contributions.
6. **Research integrity, ethics, and reproducibility:** Promoting trust, reliability, and credibility in scientific research and its outcomes.
7. **Public access to knowledge:** Making scientific knowledge accessible to the general public, and enhancing communication between scientists and society.

CROSS-CUTTING ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

OS implementation faces several obstacles and uncertainties as it aims to transform traditional research practices. Addressing them requires a multi-faceted approach, including policy changes, collaborative efforts, cultural shifts within academia, and technological advancements. Some of these challenges are:

SOCIO-CULTURAL CHALLENGES

- **Workload burden:** Researchers' already demanding workloads can lead to a minimalist approach to OS, where they merely comply with mandatory requirements.
- **Capacity-building and attitudes:** Without sufficient skills, knowledge and genuine commitment, OS principles risk becoming mere bureaucratic hurdles rather than catalysts for improved practices. Also, non-experts may struggle to critically evaluate preprints, leading to potential misinterpretations or overreliance on unverified data.

- **Competition vs. collaboration:** Limited funding, individual-focused promotion systems, and fears of scooping foster competition, impeding full idea and data sharing. Also, corporate cultures within the private sector often resist this shift due to concerns about losing competitive advantages.
- **Self-censorship** hinders honest critical feedback from reviewers, particularly regarding papers by senior researchers or sensitive topics. This reluctance stems from concerns about retaliation and damage to professional relationships. Also, many researchers avoid controversial subjects to evade backlash from funding bodies or societal groups, undermining academic freedom and limiting the diversity of perspectives. Finally, not all data analysis choices –which variables to include or exclude, how to handle missing data, etc.– are disclosed, even when it could lead to different conclusions, for fear of criticism.
- **Perceptions of quality** are compromised by stigma around paper retractions –often stemming from honest mistakes–, which obstructs self-correction. Interdisciplinary and qualitative research may be undervalued by disciplinary purists, while replication studies lack the prestige of novel research.
- **File drawer problem:** In the fast-paced global research environment, novel, positive findings are prioritized over negative or null results. This publication bias distorts scientific literature, wastes resources on duplicated research, and encourages controversial practices like HARKing or cherry-picking.
- **Bibliodiversity** in academia suffers from systemic inequities and academic extractivism. The scholarly publishing landscape often marginalizes research from diverse regions, languages, and disciplines, particularly in the Global South, where journals face scepticism regarding their credibility. These bias stems from the dominance of English-language contexts in the Global North, which shape discussions and methodologies. Furthermore, researchers from the Global North may extract knowledge from the Global South without proper recognition or collaboration, reinforcing colonial power dynamics and perpetuating inequities. Consequently, valuable insights from diverse contexts remain underrepresented or excluded from academia.

ETHICAL AND LEGAL CHALLENGES

- **Pressure to publish:** The ‘Publish or Perish’ system pressures researchers to prioritize quantity over quality instead of publishing for purpose. This encourages misconduct – such as Salami Slicing or inappropriate authorship–, leading to fragmented research, wasted resources, misinformation and false data, and diminished trust in scientific publications.
- **Publication authenticity:** Researchers, especially those early in their careers, often struggle to assess the credibility and ethical standards of publication venues, distinguishing between legitimate, predatory and ethically ambiguous hybrid journals. Additionally, identifying papers from paper mills and bronze open access adds further complexity.
- **Intellectual property:** Publishing agreements and policies can be confusing for researchers to navigate. Publishers, while primarily providing evaluation and publication services, often require exclusive copyright. This restricts authors from depositing their

preprints or postprints in repositories, translating or reusing their work on open platforms –such as Wikipedia. Also, there is an increasing misuse of IP systems (paper mills, ‘patent’ mills, fraudulent thesis writing, etc.) to inflate academic status and obtain an unfair advantage in promotion, job opportunities and prizes.

- **Data protection** involves safeguarding privacy and security, particularly for personal and sensitive information, including traditional knowledge. It is crucial to prevent data sharing from inadvertently enabling harmful practices like poaching or habitat destruction. Also, the growing ability to identify individuals in research datasets means that previously anonymous data may now be considered identifiable and thus classified as personal data.

ECONOMIC AND GOVERNANCE CHALLENGES

- **Global engagement in ORRI and OS** must prioritize accountability, collaboration, and equity while addressing power imbalances. Key challenges of science diplomacy include establishing governance for shared resources, aligning data regulations in a multi-country research environment, implementing CARE principles, and standardizing research information practices.
- **Incentive and assessment structures:** Researchers may be deterred from engaging in OS practices if there are no academic reward systems recognizing these efforts. However, responsible research assessment faces the challenge of practical implementation, determining whether and how to apply peer review, scientometrics, or a combination of both methods, in addition to context-aware assessment.
- **Monitoring:** Monitoring efforts tend to focus primarily on easily quantifiable outputs like OA publications and shared datasets, overlooking other aspects, such as cross-disciplinary collaborations, shifts in researcher attitudes towards openness, reduction or exacerbation of inequalities in science etc.
- **Financial disparities:** Lack of resources to invest in and sustain over time the technical, political, and organizational infrastructure needed to support OS practices –training, CRIS systems, APCs, translations, etc.– may deepen inequalities and restricting who can engage in OS.
- **Publishing business model:** Fully OA models require innovative solutions and collaborative efforts to restructure publishing operations that ensure long-term financial sustainability while maintaining high-quality content and services.

TECHNICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE CHALLENGES

- **Data management:** Many existing systems struggle to manage complex, large research datasets. Additionally, achieving interoperability for data sharing complicates workflows and hinders collaboration. Finally, compliance with data governance regulations needs specialized infrastructure and expertise.

- **Accessibility:** Individuals with vision impairments, learning disabilities, neurodiversity, and limited digital resources face significant barriers that restrict their full participation in research. These barriers include complex data visualizations, inappropriate contrast levels, outdated content, platform limitations, the absence of multi-format content, etc.
- **Knowledge fragmentation,** caused by scattered research outputs, impedes field comprehension and assessment. It reduces discoverability and data preservation consistency. Moreover, using unsuitable platforms –such as individual project websites– diverts resources from core research activities.
- **Research information databases:** Existing research assessment systems are often built on closed infrastructures, which reinforces bias, unsustainable dependency on commercial entities and other risks. And although non-proprietary, community-driven data sources like OpenAlex hold promise for interoperable and inclusive bibliometric analysis, their current developmental stage shows inconsistencies in data integrity, limiting the reliability of findings.
- **CERIF:** Interoperability between CERIF-based systems and other institutional systems such as HR or project management requires reconciling different data models, structures, terminologies and classifications, older systems, ensuring proper access controls and data security, keeping all integrated systems up-to-date and compatible, varying needs and priorities for data integration, etc.
- **Computational reproducibility** is often compromised by complex systems (e.g., AI), software instability, incompatibility and obsolescence. Additional barriers include lack of access to raw data, poorly formatted datasets, restrictions on sharing proprietary information, and insufficient documentation.
- **Artificial Intelligence (AI):** Integrating AI into research processes —such as scientometrics, peer review, detecting misconduct, and evaluating proposals—requires human oversight, technical robustness and safety, and protecting privacy and IPR. Also, fostering trust in AI systems needs transparency, diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness, while prioritizing environmental and societal well-being.
- **Blockchain technology** networks may struggle with the high data volumes in research. While BCT improves transparency, it raises privacy concerns for sensitive data since all transactions are visible. Also, developing and maintaining BCT infrastructure can be costly in terms of carbon emissions, water and energy consumption, and electronic waste.

MISCONCEPTIONS

Some misconceptions about OS further complicate its implementation:

- **“Open Science is solely Open Access”.** OS aims to make all aspects of the scientific process more transparent and accessible, not just the findings.
- **“Open Science requires complete openness”.** OS recognizes the need to protect sensitive information, including personal data, ecosystems and cultural heritage.

- **“Open Science contradicts IPR”**. Researchers can retain their IP rights and licence their work while sharing their knowledge. Preprints provide a time-stamped record of when an idea was proposed, and preregistration platforms also may include embargo options. Also, simply seeing an idea does not enable easy replication, and scooping is detrimental to a researcher's reputation.
- **“Open Science practices are detrimental to researchers' careers”**. Adopting OS practices can lead to higher visibility, increased citations, and greater public engagement for researchers, enhancing their reputation and credibility.
- **“Open Science lowers research quality”**. OS practices enable increased scrutiny, replication, collaboration, and dissemination of negative results. For example, working papers or preregistrations allow for quicker identification of errors and methodological improvements, and the Publish-Review-Curate (PRC) model provides transparent, community-driven evaluation.
- **“There are universal approaches to Open Science”**. There's no one-size-fits-all approach. The flexibility to adopt OS based on specific needs and contexts leads to more effective implementation.

APPENDIX B: OPEN SCIENCE AT CREAM

CREAF envisions a future where OS principles are fully integrated into all research activities, with researchers and research managers and administrators becoming OS culture-change agents. We aspire for an OS mindset to become the standard in our community through these core areas:

- **Policies:** Developing organizational frameworks and protocols that establish a common ground for implementing OS practices throughout all stages of scientific research.
- **Infrastructure:** Facilitating the technological architecture and resources that enable the implementation of OS.
- **Services:** Providing tailored guidance and technical support to make OS practices accessible and manageable for all members of our research community.
- **Culture and community:** Cultivating a community of OS advocates and practitioners through training, outreach and awareness-raising initiatives, and engagement activities to develop a collective OS mindset.

The Open Science & Knowledge Management unit coordinates, implements and oversees CREAM's Open Science strategy and offers a comprehensive service catalogue (see CREAM, 2025b) to ensure scientific knowledge creation and management processes are transparent, reliable, diverse, accessible, collaborative and integrity-driven.